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Research Article

**A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON HEMODYNAMIC CHANGES IN
CONVENTIONAL AND UNILATERAL SPINAL ANESTHESIA**¹Dr Haseeb Farooq, ²Dr Maira Pervaz, ³Dr Jawaria Abbas¹Azad Jammu & Kashmir Medical College, Muzaffarabad²Fatima Jinnah Medical University Lahore/Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore,³Bolan Medical College, Quetta**Article Received:** October 2020**Accepted:** November 2020**Published:** December 2020**Abstract:****Aim:** The aim of the study was to compare hemodynamic changes in unilateral and conventional spinal anesthesia.**Study design:** A quasi-experimental study.**Location and duration of surgery:** This study was performed in the Surgical Unit-I and Anesthesia Unit-II of Jinnah Hospital, Lahore for six-months duration from March 2020 to August 2020.**Patients and Methods:** In this study, one hundred patients who were on the list of operating rooms for an inguinal hernia were divided into two groups. Group I (n = 50) received spinal anesthesia in a sitting position, and group II (n = 50) received spinal anesthesia in the lateral position of the pressure ulcer depending on the operative side. There was no significant difference in the age and weight of the patients. Data from patients were recorded on the proforma. The comparison was made between group I and group II. Changes in heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure at different time intervals were compared.**Result:** For 100 patients; 70 patients were ASA-I and 30 patients were ASAII. The comparison was made between group I and group II. Changes in heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure at 10 minutes, 20 minutes, 30 minutes, 50 minutes, and 80 minutes after the baseline readings were compared. Baseline readings were not statistically significantly different. Mean heart rate and systolic and diastolic blood pressure were significantly reduced from baseline in both groups, but these changes in variables were insignificant in both groups.**Conclusion:** The hemodynamic stability is slightly better with unilateral spinal anesthesia, but the results are statistically insignificant.**Key words:** spinal anesthesia, inguinal herniorrhaphy, pulse, blood pressure**Corresponding author:****Dr. Haseeb Farooq,**

Azad Jammu & Kashmir Medical College, Muzaffarabad

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INTRODUCTION:

In anesthetic practice, the role of neuraxial anesthesia becomes more and more important with the passage of time. There is a large list of surgeries that can be performed under this form of anesthesia. With the development of drugs and equipment, the local anesthetic technique is being used more and more every day.

Axial nerve blockade is effective in reducing morbidity and postoperative mortality, according to some studies. Axial nerve block has been found to reduce the incidence of venous thrombosis, pulmonary embolism, bleeding and transfusion requirements, cardiac complications, vascular graft occlusion, pneumonia, and respiratory depression following upper abdominal surgery. It has also been involved in increasing tissue blood flow mediated by sympathectomy and suppressing the neuroendocrine response. Spinal anesthesia also has some drawbacks. During this technique, hypotension and bradycardia are quite common and are treated with fluids, vasopressors, and anticholinergics. These treatments can cause fluid overload, hypertension, and tachycardia, which are undesirable, especially in the elderly and patients with coronary artery disease.

Spinal anesthesia is widely used to repair inguinal hernias, providing a quick onset and effective sensory and motor blockade. Unilateral spinal anesthesia, which can also be used to repair inguinal hernia, has the effect of restricting autonomic block 2 and is helpful in high-risk patients. Reduction of blockade on the surgical side (unilateral subarachnoid anesthesia) with hyperbaric solutions, guiding needles and maintaining lateral pressure ulcers for some time has been proposed as a way to obtain high-quality and long-lasting analgesia, mainly on the operated side. In orthopedic cases, unilateral spinal anesthesia may also be beneficial, providing a deeper and more lasting block with less cardiovascular effects.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This quasi-experimental study was conducted in the Surgical Unit-I and Anesthesia Unit-II of Jinnah Hospital, Lahore for six-months duration from March 2020 to August 2020. 100 ASA I and II patients are undergoing inguinal encapsulation, were attached. Informed consent was obtained from patients during the pre-anesthesia visit. The following patients were included and excluded.

Inclusion criteria:

1. ASA I and II
2. Age between 20-50 years
3. Both men and women

4. Elective cases

Exclusion criteria:

1. Refusal on the part of the patient
2. History of allergy to local anesthesia
3. Emergencies
4. Patients with coagulation disorders
5. Infection at the site of the lumbar puncture

These 100 patients were divided into two groups: I and II. Group I (n = 50) received spinal anesthesia in a sitting position, and group II (n = 50) received spinal anesthesia in the lateral position of the pressure ulcer. The procedure was explained to the patients and informed consent was given for a pre-anesthesia visit. Upon arrival in the operating room, patients were calmed down to reduce their anxiety. In group I, monitors were used after obtaining intravenous access; basic heart rate and blood pressure readings were taken. Ringer's lactate was used to preload the patients and was administered according to the patient's weight. After the procedure had been explained and all aseptic precautions had been taken, L3 and L4 was identified and the overlying skin was soaked in 2% lidocaine. A 25 G subarachnoid needle was then inserted between the L3 and L4 intervertebral spaces, and after confirming its intrathecal position by observing a clear CSF outflow, 1.5 ml of 0.75% bupivacaine was injected. After removing the spinal needle, a sterile dressing was applied and the patient was placed in the spine position. Blood pressure and heart rate readings were taken at 10 minutes, 20 minutes, 30 minutes, 50 minutes and 80 minutes.

In group II, patients received spinal anesthesia in the lateral pressure ulcer position with dependence on the operating side. After intravenous access, monitors fitted and Ringer's lactate pre-filled with lactate, the patient was placed in a lateral pressure ulcer position. After infiltration of the skin with 2% lidocaine, a 25-gauge core needle was inserted into the L3-L4 intervertebral space. After confirmation of the IT introduction, a reduced dose of 0.75% 0.8 ml was injected slowly. Patients were held in the pressure ulcer position for 10 minutes and then placed on their backs. Blood pressure and heart rate readings were taken at 10 minutes, 20 minutes, 30 minutes, 50 minutes and 80 minutes.

Statistical analyzes:

Data was collected on a proforma and analyzed with the Social Science Statistical Package (SPSS) version 18.0. The mean and standard deviation of quantitative variables such as age, operation duration, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, and heart rate for both groups were determined. A repeated measure

of ANOVA was used to compare within-subject and between-group differences for each group. An independent sample t-test was used to compare the percent changes in mean heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure between the groups.

RESULTS:

In this study, the 100 patients were divided into two groups. Group I (n = 50) received spinal anesthesia in a sitting position, and group II (n = 50) received spinal anesthesia in the lateral position of the pressure ulcer. The mean age of the patients was 34.9 ± 12.9 years. Mean baseline heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood

pressure are also shown in Table 1. A comparison of baseline characteristics between the groups is shown in Table 2. Mean age, baseline heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure were not statistically significant between the groups. The hemodynamic changes (mean heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure) at 10 minutes, 20 minutes, 30 minutes, 50 minutes and 80 minutes were compared between the groups in Table 2. The mean heart rate at baseline was 79.8 ± 11.05 per minute in conventional spinal anesthesia and 76.27 ± 13.11 per minute in unilateral spinal anesthesia. The mean heart rate was significantly below baseline ($P > 0.1$).

Table 1: Overall characteristics of study variables (n=100)

Characteristics	Mean $\pm$ SD	95% CI	Median (IQR)	Min-Max
Age(years)	34.9 $\pm$ 12.9	32.4-39.6	35(21)	20-50
Base Line Heart Rate (per minute)	78.1 $\pm$ 12.1	77.7-84.5	81(15)	57-110
Base line systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	133.1 $\pm$ 19.3	132.9-143	133(21.3)	85-185
Base line diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)	75.0 $\pm$ 8.1	73.3-77.9	75(11)	52-93

Table 2: Comparison of hemodynamic data between groups I and II with respect to time

	Time Interval (min)	Group I		Group II		P-value
		n	Mean $\pm$ SD (mm of Hg)	n	Mean $\pm$ SD (mm of Hg)	
Heart rate (beats per min)	Base line	50	79.8 $\pm$ 11.05	50	76.27 $\pm$ 13.11	0.65
	10	50	76.15 $\pm$ 12.90	50	73.54 $\pm$ 14.43	0.89
	20	50	77.33 $\pm$ 14.93	50	68.72 $\pm$ 12.80	0.33
	30	50	69.81 $\pm$ 12.90	50	68.35 $\pm$ 13.47	0.24
	50	50	72.55 $\pm$ 10.77	50	68.35 $\pm$ 13.47	0.88
	80	3	61.10 $\pm$ 10	2	63.00 $\pm$ 14.9	0.06
Systolic Blood Pressure (mm of Hg)	Base line	50	133.38 $\pm$ 20.7	50	132.6 $\pm$ 18.1	0.96
	10	50	120.47 $\pm$ 20.7	50	120.89 $\pm$ 19.4	0.77
	20	50	115.29 $\pm$ 24.3	50	119.61 $\pm$ 19.3	0.51
	30	50	114.51 $\pm$ 23.5	50	118.29 $\pm$ 18.1	0.85
	50	50	115.10 $\pm$ 15.4	50	115.49 $\pm$ 13.8	0.84
	80	3	116.10 $\pm$ 9.1	2	123.17 $\pm$ 2.83	0.39
Diastolic Blood Pressure (mm of Hg)	Base line	50	74.6 $\pm$ 9.9	50	75.3 $\pm$ 6.90	0.36
	10	50	68.87 $\pm$ 11.1	50	69.33 $\pm$ 11.1	0.81
	20	50	63.60 $\pm$ 11.7	50	67.85 $\pm$ 10.7	0.34
	30	50	61.83 $\pm$ 14.4	50	66.47 $\pm$ 10.4	0.16
	50	50	64.35 $\pm$ 1.2	50	67.41 $\pm$ 10.6	0.29
	80	50	64.35 $\pm$ 1.2	50	67.41 $\pm$ 10.6	0.29

Baseline systolic blood pressure (SBP) was 133.38 ± 20.7 mmHg under conventional spinal anesthesia and 132.6 ± 18.1 mmHg under unilateral spinal anesthesia. Mean SBP significantly reduced from baseline ($P > 0.31$)

Baseline diastolic blood pressure was 74.6 ± 9.9 mmHg under conventional spinal anesthesia and 75.3 ± 6.90 mmHg under unilateral spinal anesthesia. The mean DBP was significantly reduced from baseline ($P < 0.0005$) in both groups, while the mean DBP was not statistically significant between the groups ($P > 0.34$).

DISCUSSION:

Several groups have described the use of unilateral spinal anesthesia to limit the extent of the spinal block to affected dermatomes, although the possibility and practicality of limiting the spinal block to the surgical site is controversial. The stability of the cardiovascular system and the discharge of patients during the operation gave positive results. Various studies have shown the effectiveness of unilateral spinal anesthesia in increasing hemodynamic stability with varying results. Since the distance between the nerve roots in the lumbar region is 15 mm, this may help to reduce blockage unilaterally. The reason for inducing unilateral blockade is to prevent hemodynamic changes and improve patient comfort. In our study, we divided patients into two groups of 50 patients.

Patients from group I underwent spinal anesthesia in a sitting position, while patients from group II underwent spinal anesthesia in a lateral pressure ulcer position depending on the operating side. A reduced dose of 0.8 ml of bupivacaine was used compared to the 1.5 ml that was given to patients in group I. The rate of drug administration is 1 ml per 20 seconds. Faster injections may result in turbulent flow patterns, resulting in greater distribution of the anesthetic towards the non-mediated side.

The most important factor in achieving a unilateral blockade is the time the patient is left in the side pressure ulcer position. Patients remained in the lateral position for 10 minutes after intrathecal injection. The privileged distribution is lost after going to a prone position. Sumi *et al.* Have shown that the lateral position of the pressure ulcer leads to a preferential intrathecal distribution of the local anesthetic solution towards the dependent side. The lateral position of the pressure ulcer appears to provide hemodynamic stability, which may reflect less sympathetic block. Sumi *et al.* Did not observe severe hypotension or bradycardia in patients who remained in the lateral position for 20 minutes. Similarly, Meyer *et al.* Observed a slight reduction in mean arterial pressure in patients who remained in the lateral pressure ulcer position after spinal anesthesia. There are many studies that favor unilateral spinal anesthesia for hemodynamic stability. Patients appeared to be placed in the lateral position of the pressure ulcer for a long time in these studies. In our study, we held the patient in a lateral position for 10 minutes, which likely caused these slight hemodynamic changes between the two groups.

CONCLUSION:

It was found that patients with unilateral spinal anesthesia showed greater hemodynamic stability compared to patients with conventional spinal anesthesia.

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